

Deliverable 3.1

Assessment report on the implementation process

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QUANTUM summary	QUANTUM aims to develop and implement a label mechanism that could be ideally adopted in the future HealthData@EU. QUANTUM builds on 5 technical work packages (WPs). WP1 conceptualises and provides technical specifications for a data quality, utility, and maturity label. WP2 designs and tests, at small-scale, the label. WP3 implements the labelling mechanism in a number of data holders. WP4 engages the data quality users' community; and, WP5 reaches out to other interested parties, including other initiatives building HealthData@EU.
Deliverable abstract	This Deliverable "Assessment report on the implementation process" addresses all aspects of the implementation process of the Quantum Labelling Mechanism tool where data holders will provide aspects like feasibility, barriers, facilitators, institutional preparedness and governance, etc., informing future international transferability and sustainability (T3.4). It will also serve as feedback to improve the tool (WP2) and future versions of the quality, utility and maturity specification (WP1). Deliverable 3.1 covers the approach, methodology, findings and recommendations for the QUANTUM tool

	implementation, resulting from QUANTUM tasks 3.1, 3.2 and 3.3.
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11	EUHA	EUROPEAN UNIVERSITY HOSPITAL ALLIANCE	BE
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14	CIPH	HRVATSKI ZAVOD ZA JAVNO ZDRAVSTVO	HR
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List of Abbreviations and Acronyms

D	Deliverable
DCAT	Data Catalog Vocabulary
DCAT-AP	Data Catalog Vocabulary Application Profile
DQM	Data Quality Maturity
DQ&U	Data Quality & Utility
EHDS	European Health Data Space
HDAB	Health Data Access Body
M	Milestone
OHDSI	Observational Health Data Sciences and Informatics
OMOP	Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership
PDF	Portable Document Format
RDF	Resource Description Framework
T	Task
WP	Work package

1 Introduction

The Horizon Europe funded QUANTUM project aims at providing guidance on a quality and utility label. Ideally, this labelling mechanism could be adopted in HealthData@EU as foreseen in the European Health Data Space (EHDS) regulation (article 78) for secondary use. The project was kicked off in the beginning of 2024 focusing on the following objectives:

1. Conceptualise and develop a data quality and utility label in the context of a data holder maturity model (WP1);
2. Design, develop and test the labelling of the data sets' quality and utility, and data holders' maturity (WP2/WP3);
3. Analyse the implementation challenges with a view to enabling the transferability and sustainability of the labelling mechanism as part of HealthData@EU (WP3);
4. Develop a capacity building and outreach program that allows a broad engagement of the data quality professional community (WP4/WP5).

This deliverable report, pertaining to WP3, provides the outcomes of the mid-scale implementation pilot of the quality & utility labels being proposed (WP1) and implemented (WP2) within QUANTUM.

1.1 Data quality & utility label

1.1.1 Fundamental concepts

When developing generic quality and utility labels for health datasets it is crucial to develop a common understanding of the fundamental concepts of quality and utility. In the QUANTUM approach:

Quality refers to features that describe the content of a dataset, typically completeness, uniqueness, accuracy, validity, timeliness, and consistency of the data.

Fitness-for-use is equivalent to a dataset's "potential" utility, typically information that describes the dataset in a standard manner, such as source, provenance or lineage, content, distribution, etc. Fit-for-use talks about the "potential" utility of a dataset, while the actual utility can only be informed by the user experience – in QUANTUM, the actual utility is referred to as fit-for-purpose.

Fitness-for-purpose refers to the actual utility of an accessed dataset according to the objective of the health data request. The information necessary to evaluate fit-for-purpose depends on the user's experience. This information needs to be added to the description of a dataset as fit-for-purpose metadata.

Maturity is a feature at the data holder level. It refers to the level of automation of data and data quality management procedures.

1.1.2 Proposed data quality & utility label

Deliverable D1.1 “Specification of the data sets’ quality and utility label”¹ provides an overview of the quality and utility label proposed by QUANTUM to be tested in the mid-scale pilot organised by WP3. The proposed label was based on desk research on data quality and utility dimensions, expert consultations and on a formal consensus process using Delphi methodology, followed by the final selection and refinement of a relevant and consensual set of criteria for assessing the quality and usefulness of datasets.

The initial comprehensive literature review and expert consultations identified 54 data quality and utility dimensions. Through iterative rounds (Delphi consensus process and an expert nominal group) and statistical validation, the list was refined arriving at 12 data quality and utility dimensions (e.g. accuracy, completeness, etc.), generic to any data reuse purpose and any type of data. It is worth noting that the utility dimension of the label in particular focuses on the fit-for-use aspects of the dataset while the actual fit-for-purpose heavily depends on the specific reuse scenario and can therefore only be determined by the user (see above for the definition of fit-for-use vs fit-for-purpose).

Subsequently, for each dimension, quantifiable metrics and scoring criteria were developed, ensuring agreement between experts from different data quality domains. For some of the dimensions, two metrics were considered necessary, resulting in 15 metrics, each with their objective scoring criteria. These were subsequently implemented in the tool developed in WP2 (see below).

1.2 Tool developed and small-scale test results

The specifications for the data quality & utility label that has been delivered by WP1 constitute the basis for the tool developed by WP2. It allows users to systematically register the quality & utility labels for any health datasets, visualise those in a user-friendly manner and subsequently export the resulting labels in a publishable format (PDF) as well as a format (RDF) compatible with most data catalogue tools and compliant with the Health DCAT-AP specification.

1.2.1 The QUANTUM data quality labelling tool

The QUANTUM Data Quality and Maturity Labelling Tool is a web-based application designed to:

- Evaluate data quality and utility through self-assessment: Enable data holders to input metadata about their datasets, facilitating the calculation of data quality according to the metrics and dimensions defined by QUANTUM partners (WP1).
- Evaluate organisational maturity: Assess the maturity level of data quality

¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14795197>

management in an organisation or entity based on a maturity matrix developed by the QUANTUM consortium (see QUANTUM D1.2 for further details)².

The tool³ is structured into two main dashboards:

1. **Data Quality Dashboard:** This dashboard allows users to self-assess the QUANTUM data quality and utility dimensions of a dataset (Figure 1). This information is then used to generate the QUANTUM data quality and utility label. Users can view the details of the computed label and its score, and download the assessment as an RDF file in .ttl format to be landed in the Health DCAT-AP specification and data quality vocabularies for interoperability with HealthData@EU standards.

Evaluate and report the following Data Quality Dimensions, within the given EHDS categories, to obtain the Dataset Quality Label

Unfold all | Fold all | 63% (To be filled / Filled)

1. Access and provision
2. Coverage
 - 2.1. Population coverage

Definition: Population coverage refers to the degree to which a dataset includes the potential eligible population.

Dimension Weight: 6.47 out of 100.

Metric #1

Definition: Coverage Rate (percentage of the eligible population represented in the dataset)

Recommended Measurement Approach: According to data holder information: (Number of individuals in the dataset / Total eligible population) x 100%

 - 2.2. Population representativity
3. Data documentation
4. Technical quality

Save changes | Go to DQ Dashboard | Download RDF | Go to DQ label

Figure 1: Two screenshots of the QUANTUM labelling tool: on the left part of the data quality and utility assessment page is shown where the metrics for the data quality label are entered and on the right the data quality certificate (“quality label”) generated by the assessment showing the attained score for each quality and utility dimension.

2. **Maturity Dashboard:** This dashboard provides an overview of the organisation’s maturity score. Users can review and update their maturity matrix values as needed, maintaining an accurate and up-to-date maturity profile.

² <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14795415>

³ https://github.com/quantum-label/quantum_labelling_tool/

The QUANTUM tool is available both as a web version and a downloadable packaged tool to be deployed within the local environment of participants in the test.⁴

Figure 2: Screenshot of the QUANTUM maturity dashboard, showing the results of the maturity assessment for an organisation.

⁴ <https://quantumpilot.upv.es/> and https://github.com/quantum-label/quantum_labelling_tool

2 High-level objectives of WP3

The high-level objectives of QUANTUM WP3 (Mid-scale implementation of the label) are:

1. Deploy the quality & utility label tool developed in WP2 in a larger group of health data holders participating in the project (“mid-scale test”).
2. Feed the learnings from the mid-scale test into WP2 to further enhance the tool.
3. Assess all aspects of the tool implementation process where data holders provide insights for transferability and sustainability.
4. Translate the outcomes of the mid-scale test into guidance for the eventual Delegated and Implementing Acts derived from the application of the legislative proposal for the HealthData@EU.

The activities of WP3 were divided into 4 tasks:

- **3.1 - Implementation plan** (Nov. 2024 - Mar. 2025). Preparations for the mid-scale test through a series of interviews with representative data holders informing the ultimate implementation plan as outlined in the milestone report⁵.
- **3.2 - Mid-scale implementation pilot** (Apr. 2025 – Dec. 2025). The execution of the mid-scale test: approach data holders to participate in the test, provide support to the test participants through a help desk, collect the test results, and interact with WP2 to incorporate the enhancements suggested by the testers in the new version of the tool.
- **3.3 - Implementation assessment** (June 2025 – Dec 2025). Overall assessment of the test user experiences provides insights into aspects like feasibility, barriers, facilitators, institutional preparedness and governance, etc., informing future transferability and sustainability (Task 3.4). It also serves as feedback to improve the tool (WP2) and for further refinement of the quality, utility and maturity specification (WP1).
- **3.4 – Transfer and sustainability** (Jan 2026 – Feb 2026). Translation of the outcomes of the mid-scale pilot to the real-life situation under HealthData@EU. Two workshops have been organised to define these conclusions and translate these into further recommendations to be incorporated in future Delegated and Implementing Acts under the EHDS.

⁵ Milestone 3.1 Implementation Plan Mid-scale Pilot - DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15341096>

3 Approach

The present deliverable report (D3.1) provides the overall summary of the findings for the mid-scale implementation pilot of the QUANTUM quality and maturity labels. It constitutes the final summary of the work executed in three tasks, T3.1 to T3.3 as outlined below. WP3 has one more task, T3.4 (Transfer & Sustainability) focused on translating the findings of the mid-scale implementation test into recommendations for future implementation of the labels under the EHDS framework. The results of this task are summarised in a separate deliverable report, D3.2 (“Guidelines and specifications for the implementation of the QUANTUM labelling mechanism as foreseen in the legislative proposal for the development of HealthData@EU, article 56”).

3.1 Implementation Plan (Task 3.1)

Task 3.1 prepared the actual mid-scale test. Ahead of the mid-scale pilot, QUANTUM carried out in-depth interviews with health data holders as prospective users of the labelling tool to assess organisational preparedness, identify potential barriers and risks, and understand expectations regarding testing and tool use. The list of interviewees was largely predetermined by the project’s Description of Action, with adjustments made for practical reasons, in particular to reach coverage over all relevant data holder types (large vs small, different data types), but also based on availability during the interview period (Jan-Feb 2025). A standardised interview guide (included as annex in the milestone report⁶) was shared in advance to gather preliminary information and to structure discussions, after which results were documented in individual interview minutes which were validated and, where needed, corrected by participants. The results were used to directly inform both the implementation plan and the practical organisation of the mid-scale test.

3.2 Mid-scale Implementation Pilot (Task 3.2)

Task 3.2 was focused on the implementation of the mid-scale pilot across a set of institutions, through the use of the tool developed by WP2, either in its online version, or the on-premise (Docker) one. At some of these institutions, both were applied in the test. Test institutions were assessing the quality of one or several datasets and the maturity of their institutions, according to the definitions established by WP1. The institutions were supported by a helpdesk (implemented as the result of M3.2) that could provide hands-on support when test users had issues getting access or difficulties navigating the tool and its quality labels. The helpdesk was also responsible for collecting the test results through an online survey.

⁶ Milestone 3.1 Implementation Plan Mid-scale Pilot - DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15341096>

The pilot has been carried out in two rounds, not necessarily with the same participants. This way, we have been able to test the tool, gather feedback from these implementers, and improve the tool according to issues and recommendations reported in their feedback. Subsequently, we organised a second round of testing collecting final feedback with comments and recommendations to guide the development of the final version of the tool. In addition, we received some recommendations on applying the QUANTUM tool in a real context.

Between the first and the second round of the pilot, some bugs and usability issues were fixed in the tool, and a cross-wp task force was organised in order to improve the knowledge base that was used to help implementers in their assessment and label-generation tasks.

3.2.1 Task objectives

At a high-level, the key responsibilities for T3.2 involved:

- Install / access the labelling tool and test the labelling process for a series of relevant datasets in a diverse and representative cross-section of data holders.
- Set up a service desk to channel issues, questions and comments from the participants, and to provide a structured knowledge base, in the form of a Frequently Asked Questions section.
- Get relevant information about the process of assessing the quality of various datasets, including tabular and non-tabular data, images, common data models, federated data models, or population-wide datasets, trying to evaluate the fitness of the tool for each of these data types.
- Get relevant information about the process of assessing the maturity of the organisations in terms of data management using the QUANTUM tool.
- Provide feedback about the experience, problems using the tool, problems translating quality and utility conceptualisation to owned datasets, problems capturing information from datasets to fulfill the labelling forms.
- Improve the QUANTUM labelling tool, and provide information from the pilot implementers that could be useful to elaborate the final recommendations about the use of the tool in a real context, and in particular in the European Health Data Space.

3.3 Implementation Assessment (Task 3.3)

The aim of Task 3.3 was to learn from the implementation experience of health data holders involved in piloting the label (T3.2) to inform the future tool implementation and of the quality, utility and maturity specification. This task complements Task 3.2 (which focuses more on technical aspects of the actual realisation in a tool) by investigating aspects related to user experience, institutional and governance aspects etc.

After both rounds of testing, we collected in-depth qualitative data to explore the following aspects:

- Feasibility of fully implementing the specification

- Satisfaction with the specifications and labelling tool
- Institutional preparedness
- Governance of the implementation
- Support for the implementation
- Barriers and facilitators
- Required resources and opportunity costs
- Transferability and sustainability of this labelling mechanism, in particular related to the interoperability of the label with existing data quality management procedures and dataset publication

Direct questions on the specifications of the tool and of the dimensions and metrics were not explicitly asked in order to focus on the experiences of the current version and to avoid replication of work in T3.2. Still, some related discussions emerged from questions on satisfaction with the tool, and this feedback was also welcome and forwarded to partners in T3.2 afterwards.

3.3.1 Round 1: Interviews

After the first round of testing, 8 semi-structured interviews were conducted with a selection of test participants, balancing the types of organisations, types and magnitude of data used for testing, and the different roles that the participants fulfil in their organisation, using the census information from Task 3.2. A discussion guide (see Annex I) was developed based on the pre-defined thematic framework (see the themes identified above) and the results from the pilot testing. An information sheet and consent form were provided to each participant beforehand outlining the aims of the pilot, the necessity of digital recording, the subsequent verbatim transcription of the session and the confidential handling of these. Each interview took around 60 minutes in a virtual setting (MS Teams) with one or sometimes more individuals from one selected organisation. One facilitator guided the conversation aiming to cover all topics, one to two note takers supported the conduct. Before commencing each interview, the rationale for the study and the specific purpose of the discussion was clearly outlined to participants.

For each interview, one of the two responsible project partners, GÖG and HIQA, was assigned to conduct the interview and perform the following analysis steps: The recordings were transcribed using MS Teams built-in function and corrected, as well as pseudonymised manually by utilising the audio recording and notes taken during the interviews. Employing a framework analysis, individual statements were extracted, annotated with a descriptive code, matched with an overarching framework (*i.e.* the topic or theme from above) and sub-themes were identified and assigned.

To ensure inter-rater agreement and improve consistency and credibility of the results, partners jointly discussed the sub-themes found and agreed upon their descriptions. A random selection of statements from each interview was cross-checked by the other partner, and all discrepancies, ambiguities or uncertainties were discussed and resolved jointly.

3.3.2 Round 2: Focus Group

A focus group was held following the second round of piloting the label to cover any gaps from round one, e.g. for underrepresented groups, to explore any issues identified in more detail and to observe changes related to the implemented improvements after round 1 testing feedback. 12 participants were recruited from 8 different organisations including those who undertook both the first and second round of testing and those who are only involved in the second round of testing.

Again, an information sheet and a consent form were prepared and provided to each participant beforehand and an adapted discussion guide (see Annex II) supported the facilitator to lead the discussion. In addition, three colleagues were available to assist the facilitator with note taking, chat monitoring and technical issues. The focus group took around 90 minutes via MS Teams.

Statements in the transcript were matched with themes in Round 1 and analysed for the “research questions” of this second round:

- To see if the main gaps identified in round 1 have been closed, and how (or if) it changed the findings;
- To observe confirmation or changes of findings in comparison to round 1, esp. related to the implemented improvements in the tool after the feedback received round 1;
- And to explore the issues most important for testers in more detail.

4 Results

4.1 Implementation Plan (Task 3.1)

The in-depth interviews with prospective participants revealed a generally high level of data quality expertise and strong motivation to engage in the mid-scale test, but also highlighted several common challenges that shaped the implementation plan. Most organisations had mature internal data quality processes but no formalised quality or utility labels, with relevant information often embedded in unstructured metadata. Interviewees expressed high expectations for automation and ease of use, alongside concerns about manual data entry and potential sensitivity of metadata, underscoring the need for clear communication on scope, limitations, and data protection. The interviews also showed wide variation in organisational maturity and tool deployment preferences (online versus local), leading to the explicit decision for the mid-scale test to include less experienced data holders, clearly manage expectations, and accommodate both deployment models. These findings were translated into concrete risk mitigation measures and support structures within the pilot design.

Building on these insights, the implementation plan for the mid-scale pilot (Task 3.2) defined a structured, phased execution between April and December 2025. The plan foresaw two main testing rounds and a (optional) smaller gap-filling round, supported by iterative tool improvements in close collaboration with WP2. Participants could use either a centrally hosted or locally deployed (Docker-based) version of the tool, supported by concise documentation, a dedicated helpdesk, ticketing system, and optional ad hoc meetings. It was stressed that data holders should be selected carefully to ensure diversity in maturity, data types, dataset size, and geographic coverage. The plan further outlined the practical details for the test as implemented in T3.2: test outcomes had to be captured through structured surveys and follow-up interviews, feeding into a broader implementation assessment (Tasks 3.3–3.4) focused on feasibility, usability, governance, and long-term transferability and sustainability of the labelling mechanism within HealthData@EU and the EHDS context.

4.2 Mid-scale Implementation Pilot (Task 3.2)

The mid-scale pilot of the QUANTUM tool was conducted across two testing rounds: the first took place between April and June 2025, and the second between October and December 2025. The primary objective of this two-round process was to facilitate an initial engagement with the tool, gather feedback from the first round, subsequently refine the tool and the associated information based on this feedback, and then execute the second round utilising the improved version of the tool.

The final feedback enabled us to assess the improvement in the perception and usability of the

tool, stemming not only from the enhancements to the tool itself, but also from the incorporated help features and tooltips offered to users, and the pilot's execution facilitated via the service desk and support documentation.

Prior to each test round, all participants were surveyed regarding the specific characteristics of their respective institutions. These factors included the type of institution, self-perceived level of maturity, and the availability of an IT department to provide support during the pilot. Additionally, their intended mode of participation was queried, covering aspects such as the rounds they wished to engage in, the preferred modality of the tool (local or online), and the number and types of datasets intended for assessment. This collected information facilitated the drafting of a participation census to evaluate the pilot's variety and representativeness. Any identified gaps in representativeness were proactively addressed by securing additional testers.

Upon the conclusion of each test round, a feedback survey (see annex III) was distributed to all participants. In both instances, 90% of the participants completed the survey.

The feedback survey covered aspects related to the following items:

- The pilot execution: Issues, problems, fulfillment
- The tool: Intuitiveness, usability and user experience
- Specification of the quality and utility label: Understandability and clearness
- Questions and response options in the tool: Understandability, fit with daily practice, ease to select and respond
- Maturity assessment: Understandability of the key metrics and questions

The survey included both categorical and open-ended questions, enabling a basic statistical analysis of the results and the compilation of a substantial collection of comments and suggestions into separate documents for each round.

4.2.1 Results from the mid-scale pilot execution - round 1

These are the main metrics from the first round of the pilot:

- Kick-off 2025-04-15
 - # Participants: 18
 - # tested Data Quality & Utility (DQ&U) label: 32
 - # tested Data Quality Maturity (DQM) label: 14
 - Number of feedback items: 125
- Finished June 2025

Table 1 shows the variety of participants in the first round of the pilot. The table shows a high level of variety between the 18 participants, although still some data types (images, federated datasets) were considered underrepresented in the group.

Table 1: Overview of the cross-section of testers (“implementers”) across organisations and data types. Those shown in red are the institutions that filled the first census survey, but indicated their willingness to participate only in the second round. Those in green are the institutions that actually carried out the pilot, and one institution (in blue) acted as HDAB, not assessing any specific dataset, but overseeing others’ datasets.

Participant	Type of institution						Maturity			IT support			contact			round				datasets		type						Tool		
	hosp	pop. repo	data hub	EDI	Acad	Other	High	med	low	inv	not inv	no it	tec	data	other	1st	2nd	both same	both dif	single	more	tab	image	non tab	CDM	pop	fed	ol	op	
Implementor 1			X				X				X		X					X			X	X							X	
Implementor 2						X	X			X		X		X				X			X	X				X	X	X	X	X
Implementor 3			X						X		X		X				X			X	X				X	X	X	X	X	X
Implementor 4		X	X					X		X		X		X		X				X	X								X	X
Implementor 5						X		X		X				X						X	X								X	X
Implementor 6	X									X		X		X		X			X	X	X	X				X	X	X	X	X
Implementor 7	X					X	X			X		X		X				X		X	X	X				X	X	X	X	X
Implementor 8	X					X	X			X		X		X				X		X	X	X				X	X	X	X	X
Implementor 9				X			X			X			X		X			X		X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Implementor 10		X						X		X		X		X		X			X	X	X	X				X	X	X	X	X
Implementor 11	X							X		X		X		X		X			X	X	X	X				X	X	X	X	X
Implementor 12	X							X		X		X		X				X		X	X	X				X	X	X	X	X
Implementor 13	X							X		X		X		X				X		X	X	X				X	X	X	X	X
Implementor 14	X					X		X		X			X		X		X			X	X	X				X	X	X	X	X
Implementor 15				X			X				X		X		X		X			X	X	X				X	X	X	X	X
Implementor 16		X					X			X			X		X				X	X	X	X				X	X	X	X	X
Implementor 17	X							X		X		X		X		X			X	X	X	X				X	X	X	X	X
Implementor 18						X		X		X		X		X				X		X	X	X				X	X	X	X	X
Implementor 19			X					X		X		X		X				X		X	X	X				X	X	X	X	X
Implementor 20					X		X			X		X		X				X		X	X	X				X	X	X	X	X
Implementor 21			X				X			X		X		X				X		X	X	X				X	X	X	X	X
Implementor 22					X			X		X		X		X				X		X	X	X				X	X	X	X	X
Implementor 23					X		X			X		X		X				X		X	X	X				X	X	X	X	X
Implementor 24			X				X			X		X		X				X		X	X	X				X	X	X	X	X
Implementor 25	X							X		X		X		X				X		X	X	X				X	X	X	X	X
Implementor 26		X																X		X	X	X				X	X	X	X	X
Implementor 27			X			X	X			X		X		X				X		X	X	X				X	X	X	X	X
Are carrying out first round																														
Only second round																														
HDAB role																														

Statistics:

The results derived from the categorical variables collected via the feedback survey are summarised in the graphs presented in Figure 3. The main conclusions are as follows:

- The majority of participants (exceeding 75%) utilised only the online version of the tool. Increased usage of the on-premise version is warranted.
- A significant number of testers encountered difficulties with the generation of the maturity label, which was attributable to an implementation error (bug). While all testers successfully completed the data quality and utility label tests, only one-third were able to complete the data maturity label test.
- The tool was generally perceived as intuitive (70% rated it as very or moderately intuitive).
- A segment of users (30%) experienced challenges in comprehending the dimensions, and the specification of these dimensions proved even more problematic (70% reported major issues).
- Finally, approximately 40% of the testers also found the questions within the tool that guide the specification of the quality label to be problematic.

Type of tool

Which assessments did you complete?

Did you find the tool intuitive?

Did you understand the dimensions clearly?

Are the specifications of the data quality dimensions clear?

Were the questions clear?

Were the answers to the questions clear?

Figure 3: Key results from the first round of testing (April-June 2025).

Regarding the narrative feedback responses, the main conclusions were:

- It would be helpful to review hints and explanations in the tool. The users wanted more help explanations, and specifically asked for real-life or prototypic examples to help

- them understand the specifications and the questions in the tool.
- Specific suggestions to review the wording of some dimensions in the specification.
- Some concepts and standards in the specification are not well known to individuals not specially trained in data quality management. More comprehensive documentation and training materials are recommended, if not essential.

4.2.2 Results from the mid-scale pilot execution - round 2

The main metrics from the second round of the pilot were these:

- Kick-off October 22nd, 2025
 - # Participants: 32
 - # tested DQ&U label: 43
 - # tested DQM label: 30
 - # feedback items: 135
- Finished November 2025
- Feedback during December 2025

Statistics:

The graphs of Figure 4 summarise the categorical results obtained from the feedback survey.

The main conclusions drawn from the tests are as follows:

- The majority of participants utilised the online version of the tool. A slight increase in the number of participants using and testing the Docker version was observed compared to round 1.
- Very few users encountered issues with implementing the maturity label, and those instances were attributable to reasons other than problems with the tool itself. The vast majority of testers were now able to complete testing for both labels, a significant improvement from round 1.
- The perception regarding intuitiveness and usability improved relative to the previous version, though it is noteworthy that over 30% of testers still rated the intuitiveness as "moderate."
- The understandability of the dimensions remained largely consistent with round 1, with 33% of respondents reporting difficulties. The clarity of the dimensions showed considerable improvement, although 45% of testers still reported issues.
- The clarity of the questions improved notably compared to the previous testing round but still requires significant refinement, as approximately 50% of the testers faced issues.

Statistics of the second round

Type of tool

Which assessments did you complete?

Did you find the tool intuitive?

Did you understand the dimensions clearly?

Are the specifications of the data quality dimensions clear?

Were the questions clear?

Were the answers to the questions clear?

Figure 4: Key results from the second round of testing (October-December 2025).

Analysis of the narrative feedback responses yields the following key conclusions:

- Despite the provision of guidance and illustrative examples to the testers, difficulties persist in the comprehension of dimensions or in the differentiation between various concepts, specifically:
 - The distinction between coherence and consistency
 - The distinction between accuracy and precision
 - The concept of "Total eligible population" (Coverage)
- A number of testers raised concerns that certain dimensions assessed quality through the availability or absence of relevant documentation, rather than by providing an objective measurement of that specific dimension.
- When implementers who participated in both evaluation rounds with the same dataset were specifically queried regarding potential quality improvement, some indicated a marginal rise in the final quality score. However, they primarily attributed this higher score not to an enhancement in dataset quality during the intervening period, but rather to a clearer comprehension of measurement methodologies for certain dimensions, facilitated by the guidance and examples available via the knowledge base and the tool itself.

Some relevant specific suggestions from the feedback are:

- Practical examples included in the tool (or well linked), not only for questions, but also for answers
- Develop a comprehensive, online "QUANTUM handbook" that formally addresses the concepts of quality and maturity dimension specification. This resource should include practical, real-world examples demonstrating the methodology for measurement and for answering the questions presented in the QUANTUM tool. Furthermore, it must incorporate a user manual to facilitate the application of the tool for assessing dataset quality and organisational maturity, making it accessible even to individuals without specialized data management expertise.

Figure 5: Comparison of the tool used and assessment completed between both rounds (in percentage of testers that completed the feedback)

Did you find the tool intuitive?

Are the specifications of the data quality dimensions clear?

Were the questions clear?

Were the answers to the questions clear?

Figure 6: Comparison of the user experience between both rounds (in percentage of testers that completed the feedback)

To provide a comprehensive overview of the overall variability across participating institutions and evaluated datasets, a consolidated table detailing the characteristics of all institutions is presented below in Table 2.

Table 2: Overall diversity of participants in the mid-scale test over both rounds of testing

Institution	Type of institution ⁷						Maturity ⁸			IT support ⁹	
	large hosp	pop. repo	data hub	EDI	Acad	Other	High	med	low	inv	not inv
Institution 1		X				X		X		X	
Institution 2	X					X		X	X	X	
Institution 3		X						X			X
Institution 4				X			X			X	
Institution 5	X							X			X
Institution 6			X			X		X			X
Institution 7	X										X
Institution 8	X				X			X			X
Institution 9	X				X			X		X	
Institution 10			X						X	X	
Institution 11		X			X		X				X
Institution 12			X				X			X	
Institution 13 (6)	X					X	X				X
Institution 14 (2)				X				X		X	
Institution 15						X		X		X	
Institution 16		X						X		X	
Institution 17						X	X			X	
Institution 18	X				X		X			X	
Institution 19	X							X			X
Institution 20						X		X			X
Institution 21					X			X			X
Institution 22	X							X			X
Institution 23		X	X		X		X			X	
Institution 24					X				X		X
Institution 25		X	X					X			X
Institution 26		X				X	X			X	
Institution 27					X	X			X		X
Institution 28		X	X			X		X			X
Institution 29		X	X					X		X	
Institution 30			X				X				X
Institution 31						X	X			X	
Institution 32	X							X			X
Institution 33			X					X		X	
Institution 34				X			X			X	

⁷ Type of institution: Large hospital, populational repository, data hub, EDIC, Academia or other

⁸ Perceived maturity level in data quality management: High, medium or low

⁹ IT support during the pilot. (inv) IT department involved in the pilot, (not inv) IT department available but not directly involved in the pilot

	round ¹⁰				datasets ¹¹		Type of dataset ¹²						Tool ¹³	
	1st	2nd	both same	both dif	single	more	tab	image	Non tab	CDM	pop	fed	ol	op
Institution 1		X			X					X			X	X
Institution 2		X			X		X		X	X	X			X
Institution 3		X			X		X						X	
Institution 4			X		X		X	X	X	X				X
Institution 5				X		X		X		X			X	
Institution 6				X		X	X						X	
Institution 7	X				X					X			X	X
Institution 8		X				X	X							X
Institution 9				X		X	X			X				X
Institution 10		X				X	X			X				X
Institution 11		X			X		X						X	X
Institution 12		X				X	X	X			X	X	X	X
Institution 13 (6)				X		X	X			X			X	
Institution 14 (2)		X			X		X				X		X	
Institution 15						X	X						X	
Institution 16			X	X		X	X	X		X	X		X	X
Institution 17		X				X	X		X	X		X	X	X
Institution 18		X				X	X		X	X		X		X
Institution 19			X		X					X			X	
Institution 20			X		X		X		X			X	X	
Institution 21		X				X	X						X	
Institution 22	X				X					X			X	
Institution 23				X		X	X			X	X	X	X	X
Institution 24				X	X		X						X	
Institution 25		X			X			X		X			X	
Institution 26		X				X	X			X	X		X	X
Institution 27				X		X	X						X	X
Institution 28			X		X		X						X	
Institution 29				X	X		X						X	
Institution 30				X		X	X		X				X	
Institution 31		X				X	X						X	
Institution 32			X		X		X			X				X
Institution 33		X			X		X						X	
Institution 34		X			X		X	X					X	

¹⁰ Round: fist only, second only, both with same dataset, both with different dataset

¹¹ Dataset: Single dataset assessed, several datasets assessed.

¹² Type of dataset: (tab) Tabular, image, (non tab) non tabular, (CDM) Common Data Model, (pop) Populational, (fed) Federated

¹³ Tool: (ol) Online tool, (op) on-premise (docker)

4.2.3 Summary results over both rounds of testing

Based on the results obtained after the two rounds of assessment, the following final conclusions have been drawn from the mid-scale pilot:

- Thirty-four institutions participated in the pilot, encompassing forty separate implementations (as some institutions tested the tool with multiple independent teams). This activity generated a total of 75 quality labels and 44 maturity labels.
- The pilot achieved a very good representativeness in terms of institution type, dataset type, and the presumed maturity level of the participating institutions, with the exception that the pilot could hardly be implemented in small organisations.
- The institutions provided highly valuable feedback, and useful recommendations were received from nearly all implementers. This detailed feedback has been compiled into two internal documents and is summarised in the present final assessment of the mid-scale pilot (this deliverable report). It will also inform the final recommendations for the implementation of the QUANTUM framework and tool within the context of the European Health Data Space (as summarised in deliverable report D3.2).
- Overall reviews concerning the usability of the tool were positive. While some testers reported the tool as moderately or slightly intuitive, all participants successfully completed the assessment without requiring assistance from the service desk, and the qualitative comments were predominantly favourable.
- The QUANTUM tool has been well-received, though clear areas for refinement have been identified, primarily focusing on enhancing the clarity of its conceptual framework and increasing the availability of practical, in-tool guidance. A recurring comment in the feedback highlighted the significant usefulness of the examples provided within the tool, as well as the need to add more real-life examples. These are required to improve understanding of both the questions related to each dimension assessment and the available answer options. Testers occasionally found that the discrete nature of the answer options made alignment with their existing knowledge and experience challenging; therefore, providing specific examples for each answer choice would be highly beneficial.
- Certain dimension definitions and topics, which exhibited generalised misunderstanding or difficulties in interpretation, have been reported to Work Packages 1, 2, and 4. This communication is intended to discuss the necessity for a more precise or readily understandable definition, clearer in-tool help information—including examples—or the incorporation of these findings into the training materials.
- Some testers who participated in both rounds of the pilot, assessing the same dataset in each instance, reported a slight improvement in the final quality score. This was not attributed to an intrinsic improvement in the quality of their datasets, but rather to a better comprehension of how to measure certain dimensions, facilitated by the aids and examples incorporated into the second version of the tool.

4.3 Implementation Assessment (Task 3.3)

Participants in the interviews and the focus group were selected from the census of health data holders involved in testing (n=26). To ensure a broad range of perspectives, profiling was carried out taking into account the type and size of organisation, the type and complexity of data held, and the self-reported maturity of the organisations' data quality practices. The characteristics of the participating organisations and their data collections can be found in Table 3.

Table 3: Characteristics of the organisations participating in the implementation assessment

type of institution	n	
	round 1	round 2
large hospital	5	2
data hub	2	3
academia	0	2
population health data repository	0	1
European data infrastructure	1	0

maturity	n	
	round 1	round 2
low	1	2
medium	3	3
high	3	3
missing	1	0

type of data	n	
	round 1	round 2
CDM	6	5
tabular	5	5
non-tabular	3	2
image	1	1
population	0	2
federated	0	1

Regarding the types of institutions, large hospitals and data hubs which will also play a big role as health data holders in EHDS secondary use of data are well represented. For academia and population health data repositories, the gap in round one could be closed in the focus group, adding these crucial voices to the assessment. All of these data holders are typically large or medium-sized organisations, potentially leaving a gap for small organisations. All levels of maturity were represented, with a slight selection bias towards more experienced organisations which tend to participate in projects like QUANTUM. Also, a wide range of data types was covered supporting the assessment of the label's agnosticity.

4.3.1 Round 1: Interviews

In total, 315 statements in 58 sub-themes in 8 themes (Barriers/Facilitators, Data quality enhancements, General Experience, Institutional Governance, Institutional Preparedness, Support/Resources, Sustainability & Transferability, Tool Satisfaction) were extracted from the interview transcripts. Irrespective of the tendency of statements, some main topics appeared quite often. See Table 4.

Table 4: Implementation assessment interviews (round 1): themes and sub-themes

Theme	Sub-theme	Statements (n)
Barriers/Facilitators		55
	Tool improvement and automation	32
	Over-seeing body and organisational co-ordination	7
	Lack of incentives	5
	Resources	3
	Reluctance to share data	3
	Quality data	2
	Good UX/UI	1
	Offer to help	1
	Metadata	1
Data quality enhancements		23
	Guidance for data quality improvement	9
	Bench-marking tool	3
	No major initiatives	3
	Present data quality improvement strategies	3
	Allocation of resources	2

Theme	Sub-theme	Statements (n)
	Improvements resulting from OMOP	2
	Completeness of metadata	1
General Experience		76
	Subjectiveness and uncertainty in answering of tool	15
	Easy to use tool	13
	Abstract terminologies and navigation challenges	10
	Quality vs. Maturity dimensions	8
	Lack of clarity in questions	6
	Possible bug identified	6
	Lack of clarity in answers	4
	Description of processes	3
	Expertise dependent	3
	Metrics calculation	2
	Lack of clarity in questions / Lack of clarity in answers	2
	Dependant on organisational setting	1
	Not time-consuming	1
	Documentation vs. Validity	1
	Time-consuming	1
Institutional Governance		26
	Existing approval and audit cycles	9
	Potential future change of processes	8
	No formal process in organisation	5
	Lack of information on governance	4
Institutional Preparedness		48
	Organisations were pre-prepared	12
	Mandatory data knowledge and expertise	12
	Organisational co-ordination required	10
	Data quality improvement practices	5
	Team coordination was prepared	3

Theme	Sub-theme	Statements (n)
	Description of processes	2
	No additional preparation required	2
	Mandatory knowledge of QUANTUM	1
	Organisation lacked skills in specific areas	1
Support/Resources		31
	Technical and legal support requirement	14
	Future support/resources	8
	No support required	6
	Description of processes	2
	Problem identification	1
Sustainability & Transferability		36
	Improvements in tool	16
	Coordination across the organisation	8
	Time and designated resources	4
	Fitting for different data types	3
	Integration of the results	3
	Training needed	1
	No major barriers for roll-out	1
Tool Satisfaction		20
	Positive remarks	10
	Negative remarks	10

Overall, participants confirmed the tool's value as a comprehensive and relevant framework for assessing data quality and maturity. The feature of both an online and offline tool allows for easy accessibility, providing an intuitive and visually appealing interface. However, the feedback highlights several critical areas that require attention before the tool's wider implementation.

The most significant challenge was ambiguity in the tool's content. Participants consistently reported that questions and answers were often abstract and open to subjective interpretation. The lack of clarity in both the questions and the answers' options was the primary contributor to user uncertainty and the time-consuming nature of completing the tool.

It was commonly perceived by data holders that the Quality aspect of the tool was self-explanatory and intuitive to answer, while the Maturity aspect demanded a different level of expertise from someone with governance oversight within the organisation.

The participants expressed readiness for the broader implementation of the tool. However, for organisation-wide implementation participants highlighted that success would only be possible by steps such as the establishment of a central coordination function and the clarification of roles and responsibilities. They expressed that these needs provide an incentive for their organisations to improve by adapting processes and coordinating teams better.

4.3.1.1 General experience

Participants reported a generally **positive user experience** with the tool's interface and navigation, but faced significant challenges with the clarity of questions, particularly for the data maturity section of the tool. They consistently noted a difference in the **difficulty of completing the data maturity section** compared to the data quality section, describing the data quality aspect as '*quite self-explanatory*', and the organisational maturity aspect as '*a bit harder*'. The data maturity section often required consultation with senior staff familiar with organisational governance processes, whereas the data quality section generally required familiarity with the dataset itself, an expertise that most users involved in the pilot had.

Across organisations, the clarity of both the questions and the provided answer options was a common point of criticism. Participants described the questions as '*too abstract*', '*short*', and '*lacking detailed descriptions*'. A significant challenge reported by users was the potential **subjectivity of the tool's question statements**, which created uncertainty when providing answers within the metrics. Participants often had to interpret questions based on their own understanding, raising concerns about the accuracy and comparability of responses.

Several participants explained that they '*cannot guarantee the validity of their results*'. It was suggested that this subjectivity in answering could be mitigated by providing guidance or examples on how each question should be interpreted and how specific answers should be reached, enabling more consistent revisions at later stages. Furthermore, a critical observation from a participant was that the tool's focus on **documenting processes does not necessarily guarantee the actual validity of the quality of data**. The participant argued that measuring documentation is easier but insufficient and further suggested that questions should explore active quality assurance practices rather than just the existence of documentation.

Despite some challenges, many participants identified positive aspects of the tool's usability. It was described as **intuitive, visually appealing, user-friendly and easy-to-navigate**. Participants acknowledged that the tool covered the correct dimensions of data quality and maturity. However, the process of filling out the tool was perceived by some as '*slow and time-consuming*', largely due to the need to interpret **vague questions**. Some participants encountered technical issues, suggesting the **possibility of bugs** within the tool. Some reported that previous answers had been reset upon logging back in and incidents where selected answers would not save correctly or were labelled as missing. Users also reported technical

difficulty in the downloading and installation of the offline version of the tool. Such technical feedback was reported to task 3.2 engaged in versioning and improving the tool.

4.3.1.2 Institutional preparedness

Some participants reported that their institutions generally **did not require significant additional preparation** to test the tool as the necessary information was readily available. This was often because those involved had participated in European research initiatives that had required strong data governance, with regular data quality reviews and reporting already in place. Institutions utilising standardised data models, such as the OMOP common data model, were especially well prepared to complete the tool. Participants from these organisations found it easier to answer *'the data quality tool's questions'*, noting that the metrics aligned closely with processes they routinely used to report similar data quality metrics.

Effective coordination across different departments was identified as not just beneficial but mandatory for accurately completing the tool. Participants emphasised the need for collaboration between IT services, hospital information systems, scientific directions and clinical teams, noting that a single individual may not be able to provide all the required information. The necessity of a multi-disciplinary approach was highlighted by a participant as *'I don't think that a data manager who is not talking to the hospital information system will be able to answer all the questions'*. This collaboration was also seen as vital for continuous quality improvement of data.

Participants identified the need for **deep knowledge of the specific dataset** as an essential prerequisite for completing the tool. Technical staff involved in data creation and mapping were considered better positioned to complete the data quality aspect of the tool. Whereas the knowledge of organisational procedures, legal compliance and the fundamental data quality dimensions was mandatory to answer the maturity aspect of the tool, creating a need to involve several experts and levels (data experts versus senior managers) within an organisation.

Certain participants noted a **lack of expertise within the organisation** to complete the tool effectively. In such cases, participants sought support from external expertise or from individuals involved at the source of data collection for centralised datasets such as biobanks. This was particularly common when addressing questions related to data provenance where detailed knowledge of the source data and the data pathway was required.

4.3.1.3 Institutional governance

Feedback revealed that formal governance pathways for such an assessment are currently often underdeveloped with **approval processes remaining informal** or currently not in place for many participants. A prominent finding was that many individuals directly involved in the testing of the tool lacked detailed knowledge of their organisation's formal data governance policies and approval workflows. This was particularly evident among technical staff, who often operated without clear insight into overarching governance frameworks. As this was a pilot

testing of the tool, most participants reported that no formal internal approval or ethics review was required. However, the absence of structured oversight was interpreted not as a barrier to progress, but that further consideration needed to be given to the governance system supporting the label. In some cases, sign-off was handled informally by a single individual which may be insufficient for future formal submissions of the label for public release that may require executive sign-off as an essential governance procedure.

In contrast, some organisations demonstrated **elements of good governance** with established approval bodies and audit mechanisms in place. Participants from these organisations indicated that a wider rollout of the tool would involve engagement with existing structures such as Data Protection Officers and Data Oversight Committees. The validation of the tool's answers was seen as a specialised task, with a participant concluding that this would only be possible for a very restricted team of people with the necessary insight into the dataset itself. Therefore, piloting of the tool has prompted **expectations for formalising new governance processes**. While immediate large-scale changes were not considered necessary, organisations recognised gaps that would need to be documented and formalised. Participants reported plans to integrate the tool's specific quality checks into internal data quality management procedures.

4.3.1.4 Support and resources required to utilise the tool

Some users required **no additional support** to complete the tool in this pilot phase. This self-sufficiency was largely attributed to their pre-existing technical expertise and knowledge of datasets (the reason they were chosen for the pilot). However, participants identified clear scenarios where external support would be essential for broader implementation. Technical support was deemed necessary for users without a strong data management background, and legal support was highlighted as critical for answering the maturity section, though challenging to procure. Users also sought **peer-support** for understanding ambiguous questions and emphasised the need for guidance. Users expressed a desire for **walkthroughs or demonstrations** using example datasets to understand the rationale behind scoring systems.

Looking forward, participants predicted that successful long-term implementation of the tool would require **dedicated roles and responsibilities**, and potentially new technologies. As the pilot focused on one dataset, participants did recognise that a designated data governance professional or team would be required to coordinate the completion of the tool across all relevant datasets and mobilise resources across the organisation for continuous quality improvements in line with the label's results.

Additionally, AI technologies were seen as a potential future resource for improving data quality, particularly for **unstructured data**, though current projects were described as not yet successful. Participants from institutions utilising the OMOP Common Data Model highlighted the Observational Health Data Sciences and Informatics (OHDSI) community as a valuable external resource in providing **standardised tools and definitions**. Those involved in using OMOP described advanced data quality practices that helped simplify the completion of the tool.

4.3.1.5 Data quality enhancement initiatives resulting from the tool

While the tool did not immediately trigger new quality projects, it was widely endorsed as a **vital strategic guideline for future data quality improvements**. Several participants reported that the tool's assessment did not lead to significant quality enhancement initiatives, as their scores generated by the tool aligned with their existing understanding of their data's quality. However, they stated that it effectively consolidates essential dimensions of data quality into a **single structured framework** bringing together previously ad-hoc aspects.

A key insight was that any significant quality improvement driven by the tool's results would be dependent on the **allocation of roles and responsibilities**, as improving quality scores would be a challenging task without dedicated resources. Participants suggested that the tool's ability to inspire action would be significantly enhanced if it included a **benchmarking function** and **specific recommendations to improve data quality**. The current lack of comparative data or suggested improvement paths was seen as a missed opportunity. Furthermore, the piloting of the tool identified **metadata completeness** as a critical pre-requisite, leading to institutional plans to enhance metadata compilation at a faster pace by dedicating responsibilities to this task.

4.3.1.6 Barriers and facilitators to sustainability and transferability

The tool's long-term sustainability relies on addressing significant barriers such as **high resource demands and organisational culture**, with **tool automation and technical enhancement** identified as the primary facilitators. Time and specific expertise were identified as considerable barriers. Participants noted that applying the tool across a magnitude of datasets within larger organisations would demand significant effort and coordination therefore **questioning scalability without dedicated data handling roles**. This challenge is compounded in complex healthcare settings like hospitals, where the process becomes particularly time-consuming for each dataset.

A significant cultural barrier identified within institutions is a **reluctance to share data**, due to the lack of perceived immediate benefits by the data holders. Participants reported that clinicians and data creators are often hesitant to share data - both internally and externally - without tangible incentives, as generating high-quality data requires substantial time and resources. Consequently, it is understandable to wish for remaining the primary beneficiary of such data.

The absence of an overseeing body within an organisation and lack of **central coordination** hinder the tool's broader implementation across multiple datasets. Participants suggested that identifying the right person with the right knowledge is a major challenge, given that the tool may require staff at different levels to generate the responses, validate the information and sign-off prior to submission, while simultaneously following steps to examine and implement required quality improvements to maintain and improve scores. Some statements expressed the perception of the tool as being tailored for clinical data, foreseeing difficulties in applying it to genomic, imaging or other complex data types and indicating a need for **adaptations** and

examples to be equally efficient **for non-tabular data**.

The most frequently suggested facilitator was a series of technical improvements to the tool itself. **Automation of the tool** emerged as a key solution to reduce the time and cognitive burden of the task. Participants recommended providing more precise descriptions, more examples, and additional tool tips. Users also highlighted the need for improved guidance and training to better understand dimension definitions and scoring criteria, particularly for new users. Although the QUANTUM academy tutorials aid in basic education, **integrated guidance, pre-assessment training, and clearer examples** within the tool itself were identified as significant facilitators for broader implementation.

4.3.1.7 Overall tool satisfaction

In summary, participants highlighted several strengths of the tool. They appreciated its clear, user-friendly interface, which allows for easy navigation and delivers well-structured results. The transparent scoring logic, showing how ratings and star levels are calculated was seen as a key factor in building user trust. Additionally, the tool's emphasis on metadata and documentation was considered a practical and accessible approach, particularly for users with expertise in metadata rather than advanced data analytics. This focus enhances its applicability across diverse organisations.

However, practical use revealed areas for improvement. Participants noted that some questions could be phrased more clearly and suggested adding concrete examples to fill gaps in understanding. Users also found the impact of specific responses on final scores somewhat ambiguous, creating uncertainty and potential for subjective interpretation. Furthermore, they observed that the feedback provided lacked actionable guidance for improving low scores.

4.3.2 Round 2: Focus Group

One relevant gap identified in round 1 was the **underrepresentation** of some types of data holding organisations. For academia and population health data repositories this gap could be closed in the focus group (see Table 3). Still, **small organisations** were underrepresented in both rounds. This is due to a general selection bias: small data holders fully occupied with their daily business are less likely to participate in projects like QUANTUM, to know about or be interested in EHDS, to be active in networks and therefore recruitable for such endeavours, and to have the capabilities to participate. Nevertheless, we observed in both rounds that the fragmentation of organisations can have a similar effect, e.g. a small specialised department in a larger organisation that works relatively independently can have similar challenges like the lack of defined procedures or the full range of experts at hand that are needed to easily implement all aspects in the label.

This finding from round 1 was reiterated several times in the focus group discussion, once phrased as "*being able to fill in this properly would require quite **many different people from different roles and different perspectives***". The roles of data owners, data managers, clinical informaticians, data scientists, metadata experts and people with technical expertise were

mentioned explicitly, and support and guidance by HDABs and the organisations themselves was desired. The concern was raised that in organisations without all necessary roles and support involved in completing the tool would result in *"making some wild guesses in order to answer the tool"*. Also clear guidance in what role / expertise would be needed to answer each section was considered helpful.

Continuity was also considered a problem: *"We did not know how to answer directly because the people involved in this kind of assessment are no longer part of the system [...] he implemented the whole database in the health system, he's the one with the knowledge of the data model and the in-depth knowledge of the data set itself, but he's not in his position, so I had to ask him now in his new position, about the original database."* Of course, such a loss of expertise can happen to all organisations, but the risk is certainly higher for small data holders.

Another relevant gap in round one was that several participants had reported difficulties in answering the **maturity part of the label**. In this second round, all self-reported levels of maturity were present. One participant from a very mature organisation found the maturity part easier to answer than the data quality and utility part, one participant from a public health institute found them equally challenging, and one reported that *"colleagues from a medical registry struggled with the maturity part. And I think that reflects that these are people working very close to the data"*. The lesson to be learned here is that mature organisations are, unsurprisingly, also better able to answer questions relating to organisational aspects in such a tool. This seems logical, but it also highlights the following problem: less mature organisations should also be able to easily complete the part of the tool devoted to maturity. Only then will the results be useful to organisations, helping them to identify areas for improvement and, ultimately, to strengthen their maturity over time.

A related issue was also raised: a proper maturity and quality assessments often requires multiple roles in the organisation while it is usually done by one person only: *"in the majority of the organisations the maturity label is filled in once, then maybe it will be quite different people being responsible for the dataset Quality and utility label"*.

The discussion showed another issue related to the **maturity assessment**, which cannot always be answered per organisation, but **could require separate assessments per dataset**: *"We can't provide maturity on the level of our organisation because it wouldn't make any sense. So we need to put it down to the level of the single datasets, because we have very different procedures, very different pipelines"*. Three participants had observed that same situation. So in general the maturity part should refer to that part of an organisation that operates under a common set of data management practices . This will often correspond to the organisation as a whole. However, in some institutions, multiple practices and internal rules coexist in parallel, sometimes due to grown structures and sometimes due to different applicable rules.

Also, the distinction between the maturity assessment and dataset related quality aspects was not clear enough for all participants expressing that *"some of the questions and some of the text in the maturity assessment actually refer to a dataset, so it was quite confusing"*. Some of these questions were seen as *"actually like practical and even telling a little bit more of technical quality"*.

Several types of data have been covered in both rounds (see Table 4). A gap identified in round one was addressed in round two by adding population health data and federated data, which

helped to review the nature of the tool being **agnostic to data types**. However, the fact that the label tries to achieve this by informing about the level of documentation in some metrics (“it seems to measure more of the quality of reporting on the quality than the actual quality”) was questioned: “How well does the tool assess what it’s meant to assess? If I say for example, I have documented completeness, and it’s zero, so maybe that response would be a perfect score and I don’t know if that represents what it was meant to represent”. It was acknowledged though that such a documentation of completeness would provide a user with the means to explore the respective quality dimension, instead of reflecting the quality dimension directly in the label.

Most other topics covered in the discussion reinforced the learnings from round one. **Satisfaction with the tool itself** was high (“very easy to navigate and very user friendly”), as well as with deployment of both technical variants which “went smoothly” or “worked perfectly”. So the way how feedback was implemented and issues and bugs were resolved was endorsed. This is a relevant learning for future maintenance of the tool, asking for continuing and reactive development.

Several statements emphasised the finding from round 1 that organisations see the challenge of having to apply a new label under EHDS as a chance to enhance their data quality (management). They think about ways to improve, how to feed the learnings from this new duty back into their actual business to generate a benefit from it, and how to best integrate this new high-level view on quality with the accustomed more specific ones:

- “One of the positive things with this tool is that it inspires more discussions in the organisation about how we document quality. We are quite skilled at documenting quality, but we do it mostly like an internal procedure and very cancer specific things and we are not that used to lifting it up to this more general level”.
- “Our quality checks are much more specific than the ones asked here.”
- “Okay, this is EHDS territory, this is how people will look at data quality. Thinking of how we go from a higher meta-view on quality to very specific data quality requirements where you look at individual level. It pushed us to look at data quality from a different perspective.”
- “I got that input from my colleagues as well that using the tool they discovered some metrics or some things that they should actually be doing.”

Participants also formulated wishes related to transferability:

- “We would very much like to see some more integration with HealthDCAT-AP metadata variables”.
- “And some more ... let’s say FAIR-ness machine actionability in order to support researchers”.

The **biggest topic** that was discussed the most during this focus group relates to **examples, more guidance and clearer instructions**. More examples are strongly needed, they should be simple, easy to understand and also provide understanding of the single answer options. They should not require too much specific knowledge: “There was something for example related to PROV-O. And people just don’t know what it is.”

Where such knowledge or context is necessary explanations should be given, including “some guidance on how to prepare for filling out this quality label. What would you be advised to do before you start filling this out?”

Also health data holders should be able to add context information, e.g. coverage rate could be interpreted much better in context with sampling strategy.

Greater clarity is also seen as being important for a harmonised implementation across all EHDS participants to support comparability.

There is also a concern that **comparability and objectivity** will not easily be achieved, potentially undermining the credibility of the tool and label: *“The first labels won't represent the truth. [...] in a regional system, you will want that your average point is better than the points around you. So you will say, what can I do to change those values [...] But the validity of the tool itself will be questioned the first time you pass it. [...] This has been one of the biggest worries from our management that it will not actually reflect the quality of the datasets. It will reflect the self-assessment which will maybe make it biased”*. Therefore, the responsibility of HDABs to monitor the quality of the labelling itself (Art. 78(4) EHDS) will be crucial.

5 Conclusions and discussion

In this final section of the report we will summarise the overall conclusions of the mid-scale test and the subsequent interviews and focus groups. We will also share some general considerations and limitations of our mid-scale test.

The further translation to concrete recommendations for inclusion in EHDS-related guidelines and further refinement of the label framework is in parallel taken up by task 3.4 (“Transfer and sustainability”). That work will be summarised in Deliverable report D3.2 (Guidelines and specifications for the implementation of the QUANTUM labelling mechanism as foreseen in the legislative proposal for the development of HealthData@EU, Article 56).

5.1 Key findings of the mid-scale test

The implementation of the QUANTUM Data Quality & Utility and the Maturity labels have been extensively reviewed in T3.2 (mid-scale test) and T3.3 (implementation assessment). The previous chapter of this report has summarised the results of these tasks in separate sections. In the list below, we condensed the results of both tasks:

- **Feasibility/satisfaction.** Implementers reported that the tool was easy to use and an easy way to assess datasets and generate the DQ&U label. However, more detailed guidance and real-life examples are needed to better understand how to implement an assessment. In time, the introduction of benchmarking and improvement recommendations could potentially lead to enhanced peer learning and quality enhancement initiatives.
- **Maturity assessment.** The scope of the organisation concept must be rethought in complex institutions with different levels of maturity between departments. The process for evaluating multiple similar datasets should be made easier.
- **User experience.** Enhance the clarity and intuitiveness of colour coding within the tool to improve user experience. For example, align similar colours across categories and associated dimensions defined in the quality tool and ensure consistency with established practices in the output report such as using green to indicate good quality practices.
- **Enhanced governance.** Several testers encountered difficulties in implementing the maturity label due to lack of knowledge regarding data governance and oversight. In some instances, the implementers had a highly technical background, which proved essential to complete the data quality assessment. However, some were not responsible for data governance within their respective institutions, leading to an inability to provide the required answers for the maturity assessment. Therefore, to support the optimal assessment and reporting of the data quality and utility tool, organisations should ensure that those with appropriate knowledge for the data quality and maturity assessments are involved at key stages of decision making. In addition, this deficit in data governance knowledge or experience may be particularly

pronounced in smaller institutions, such as small or medium-sized hospitals, which were underrepresented in testing. All organisations, even large ones, need to prepare, to gather expertise from several roles, and to consider developing an internal process for smooth routine implementation.

- **Workflow support.** During the mid-scale pilot, the majority of testers evaluated a single dataset, with a few assessing a small number of datasets. In a realistic operational environment, institutions may need to evaluate a substantial quantity of datasets, which could entail a considerable workload and time commitment. It would be beneficial if the tool incorporated a mechanism to streamline this process, such as the capability to define "data quality templates" with common predefined attributes, allowing for the replication and modification of these attributes for each dataset as necessary. In time, it would be optimal to provide an option of automating the process or at least streamlining the completion of multiple labels within one organisation with many datasets by providing the functionality to pre-fill assessment fields that are similar across datasets. The benefit of this would be twofold as it should also facilitate a reduction in manual errors.
- **QUANTUM Handbook.** In addition to the widely expressed need for practical examples to illustrate the definitions of dimensions, questions, and answers within the quality and utility assessments, the preparation of a "QUANTUM Handbook" has been proposed. This resource would consolidate the conceptualisation of quality, utility, and maturity in a single location or document, providing clear explanations of the dimensions, including examples and any useful supplementary information, along with the "QUANTUM tool user manual."

5.2 Discussion

While we executed quite an extensive and representative mid-scale test, some methodological questions and concerns might still be raised:

- **Self-assessment bias.** Even with the abovementioned QUANTUM Handbook alleviating the problem of inconsistent assessments, there is still the risk of biased results due to pressure to perform well. The role of HDABs in monitoring realistic assessments will be crucial in promoting comparability and objectivity of labels.
- **Selection bias.** Participating organisations had well-established data management processes and prior involvement in the QUANTUM project. Consequently, the pilot assessment provided valuable feedback on the tool's functionality and conceptual framework from organisations that were well-prepared for implementation. However, a gap exists in terms of less mature and smaller organisations. Therefore, the implementation of the label should be further considered in terms of the application for organisations at earlier stages of maturity along the data quality journey. Furthermore, for wider roll-out, the tool's design and supporting resources must evolve to accommodate a broader spectrum of organisational maturity levels and dataset types, ensuring it remains accessible and useful for all organisations and for the wide

diversity of datasets.

- **Generalisability of the assessment (dimensions).** The aim of the assessment in T3.3 was to explore the experiences of data holders involved in piloting the label and not to assess the specifications of the dimensions as defined in WP1/2. Although some participants commented when asked about their experiences or satisfaction with using the tool, broader considerations on the dimensions included in the tool was out of scope of this task. The relevance of the dimensions could also have different implications for the application of the label in practice for smaller and less mature organisations and datasets. This may need to be considered further.
- **Risk of false expectations.** It is acknowledged that the label is designed to be agnostic to data types. In some dimensions, it can therefore not show the actual data quality but the quality of documentation, which is an entry point to the sought information. False expectations should be avoided about what the label can and cannot provide.
- **Further integration needed.** The label provides a high-level view on data quality, which organisations see as a beneficial complement to their own specialised and detailed view. Integrating both is seen as a chance to improve their own understanding and their quality management processes as well as a challenge demanding for further exploration, e.g. in projects like CancerWatch.

Annex I Discussion Guide – Interviews to assess the mid-scale implementation of the QUANTUM tool, Round 1

Duration: Each interview will last approximately 45-60 minutes.

Location: MS Teams

In attendance:

- [Add number of participants] number of participant(s) from participating organisation
- 1 facilitator (GÖG/HIQA)
- 1-2 note takers (1 note taker will also act as the contact person for participants having technical issues etc.) (GÖG/HIQA)

Introduction and presentation

Introductory script

- Hello my name is [insert name of facilitator] and I work for GÖG/HIQA. This work is being organised as part of the QUANTUM project, which as you are aware, aims to create a quality and utility for datasets in Europe.
- The aim of the pilot, which you have already completed, is to test the labelling tool with data holders. The purpose of these interviews are to discuss your experience in using the QUANTUM tool.
- Feedback related to the tool itself (UX) or to the specifications is out-of-scope today, of course we will take up such information as well. --> ticketing system, survey (received? to be expected).
- The interview should take approx. 60 minutes. Please note that this assessment aims to cover different topics to that in the survey that was sent for input on.
- [Introduce QUANTUM team] This task is being led by both HIQA and GÖG. I will facilitate the group (ask questions and guide the discussion). [Add name of notetaker] will be taking notes of the discussion. If you have any technical difficulties, please email [add mail address].
- Obtain verbal consent from participants that they are happy for the session to be recorded and notes to be taken.
- [Start recording]
- Emphasise that the interview is confidential. We will be taking notes of the discussion but any comments you make will not be linked to your name or any other personal details. It will not be possible to identify any individual in the findings and no information will be provided to anyone that could identify you.
- Please feel free to ask questions if you would like something to be repeated or explained more clearly.
- Participation is voluntary and you have the right to withdraw from the interview at any time.

- Thanks for agreeing to participate.

Opening questions

- What was your role and involvement in the testing?
- What dataset did you do the testing on?
- Did you also complete the maturity model part?
- In general, what was your experience with completing the QUANTUM tool?

1. Institutional preparedness

a. Explain any preparation you did for testing the QUANTUM label?

- Was information readily available to easily answer questions?
- Was additional work required to gather sufficient information to answer each question?
- Please explain or give examples.

b. Who was involved in gathering information and completing the tool?

- Was it clear who (which roles) in your organisation should be tasked with coordinating the completion of the tool?
- Did staff members involved have the necessary knowledge to complete the tool effectively?
- Was there any particular question(s) you found hard to complete?
- Did they have to consult other teams/individuals/externally?

c. Will your organisation need to make any changes to process or work flows to complete this information frequently/each year?

2. Governance of the implementation

a. What governance decisions were required during the pilot or will be required going forward?

- Any changes required for full implementation?
- E.g. Oversight, approvals, auditing, improvements
- Oversight regarding accurate completion of the tool (sign-off from senior management)
- Learnings emerging from the completion of the tool are actioned/audited?

b. Does the tool complement other internal or external data governance structures/findings?

- Does this align with broader organisational data quality strategy?

3. Support/resources for the implementation

a. Explain if you used the online version or locally installed version (both) and your experience?

b. What support was required for the implementation of the tool in your organisation?

- HR/staffing - effort required to complete/implement the tool

- Technical resources IT - did you experience any technical issues that required additional assistance?
 - Upskilling – going forward will any training/upskilling be required? E.g. Oversight, approvals, auditing, improvements
 - Other support required - did implementation require significant involvement from any other departmental/external support?
- c. What additional support will be required to implement this tool on an ongoing basis?**
- d. Who will be responsible for coordinating completion each year?**
- e. Any additional changes required?**

4. Barriers and facilitators

- a. What were the main challenges or obstacles you faced during the pilot?**
- Was it self-explanatory? Was there a need for additional details regarding the tool, the specifications and questions etc.?
- b. What do you anticipate as the challenges and solutions to this going forward?**
- c. What advice would you give to others planning to use this tool?**

5. Transferability and sustainability

- a. In your opinion what must be in place before scaling the tool to other datasets and areas?**
- How many other datasets need label applied?
 - Do you think this tool would work for other datasets in your organisation?
 - How well does the tool integrate with your existing systems?
 - What are your thoughts on the interoperability with this tool and your organisations existing data management procedures and datasets?
 - Are there foreseeable challenges to rolling it out more broadly?
 - What changes (if any) would be required in order to do this?
- b. How well can you interpret the outcomes of the tool? Can the outcomes be used for organisation?**

6. Other questions

- a. Has this tool changed/will it change how you or your team approach data quality?**
- b. What did you miss in the tool, what functionality could improve its value for your organisation?**
- c. After the pilot, how satisfied are you with the specifications and labelling of the tool?**
- d. Have you used any other data quality tools before? If so, how does this one compare?**
- e. Is there anything else that we've not covered today that you'd like to highlight or discuss?**

Close

- Next steps: this is phase one of the pilot and of the assessment of the experience of those involved. Phase two will take place in September/October, which will include

focus groups. Maybe in contact in due course around participation in these.

- Thanks for taking part. If you have any further queries, you can contact us by emailing [insert mail address].

Annex II Discussion Guide – Focus group to assess the mid-scale implementation of the QUANTUM tool, Round 2

Duration: The focus group will last approximately 1.5 hours including the introductions.

Location: Teams

Time: [...]

In attendance:

- [Add number of participants] number of participant(s) from participating organisation
- 1 facilitator: GÖG
- 1 person moderating & raised hands, time keeping: HIQA
- Monitoring the chat: HIQA
- 1 note takers: HIQA
- 1 technical issues, ensure the session is recorded: GÖG
- Participants: [Mail address from participant] Interview round 1: Yes or No

Introduction and presentation

Introductory script [5 min]

- Hello, my name is [insert name of facilitator] and I work for Gesundheit Österreich GmbH (GÖG). This work is being organised as part of the QUANTUM project, which, as you are aware, aims to create a quality and utility label for datasets in Europe.
- [Introduce QUANTUM team] This task is being led by both HIQA (the Health Information and Quality Authority in Ireland) and GÖG with representatives from both teams here today to facilitate the discussion. I will facilitate the group (ask questions and guide the discussion), others will jump in when necessary. [Insert name of notetaker] will be taking notes of the discussion. If you have any technical difficulties, please put it in the chat or email [insert mail address].
- [Aim] The aim of the pilot, which you have already completed, is to test the labelling tool with data holders. The purpose of this focus group is to discuss your experience in using the QUANTUM tool.
- After phase one of the testing of the tool we carried out 8 individual interviews. Now this group has participants from both phase one and phase two of the testing as well as some who took part in the interviews earlier in the year.
- The focus group should take approx. 1 hour and 30 minutes. Please note that this assessment aims to cover topics different to that in the survey that was sent for input on.
- [Consent] Not everyone has filled out the consent form, so I ask you for your verbal consent now. We will record this session and take notes. Both are not shared (not even within the project) and only used by us, HIQA & GÖG, for our analysis, and only

aggregated results or anonymised quotes are used in any outcome. Therefore, it will not be possible to identify any individual in the findings, and no information will be provided to anyone that could identify you.

Participation is voluntary and you have the right to withdraw from the interview at any time.

Are you happy for the session to be recorded and notes to be taken?

- [Add name of person], please start the recording.
- Please feel free to ask questions if you would like something to be repeated or explained more clearly.
- And please be as honest and open in your comments as possible - any kind of feedback is appreciated and helpful.
- Thanks for agreeing to participate.
- A note on the questions. The majority of questions are to all participants; however, some are only suitable for those who carried out both phases – this will be highlighted.
- Shall we have a short introductory round of each participant? If you just quickly say your name, the institution, and in which of the activities you have participated, that would be a nice overview.

1. General experience + tool satisfaction [15 mins]

a. In general, what was your experience with completing this version of the QUANTUM tool?

- How did you find the interface of the tool, esp. its usability?
- Considering the user experience: Things like accessibility, intuitive usage etc. are there any suggested enhancements to improve?
- How did you find completing the different sections of the tool - the data quality and utility section and the maturity section?
- Regarding the result of the tool: Were you satisfied with the report generated? What do you think about the benchmarking it enables?
- [Participants in phase one] Has the tool improved since the first phase? Has the addition of captions / instructions improved clarity?

2. Institutional preparedness [15 mins]

a. Please explain the data preparation you did for testing the data quality and utility label.

- Was information readily available to easily answer questions?
- If not, what additional work was required to gather sufficient information to answer each question? Please explain or give examples.
- [Participants in phase one] After the initial round of testing, did you do anything differently or do you undergo any additional data preparation to be better prepared for the second round of testing?
- Who was involved in gathering information and completing the tool, meaning which roles in your organisation?
- Was it clear who in your organisation should be tasked with coordinating the

completion of the tool?

- Did you (or those involved) have the necessary knowledge and data to complete the tool effectively or did you have to consult other teams/individuals/externally?
- [Participants in phase one] Some participants in phase one reported issues with ensuring the correct people were involved in filling out the info for the tool. Was there a need to get additional people involved after the first round?

3. Institutional governance [15 mins]

a. As the label is implemented and reported publicly, governance at an organisation level will be important in terms of coordination, oversight, approvals, auditing and improvements. What governance decisions were required during the pilot or will be required going forward?

- Is it clear or has it been discussed who in the organisation will provide oversight and sign off prior to the label being submitted?
- If yes, does this align with broader organisational data quality structures and strategies?
- If not, are there plans to put governance structures in place?
- [Participants in phase one] Have any further discussions on governance of the tool or of data quality in general been prompted by the participation in phase one?

4. Support / resources for the implementation [15 mins]

a. What support was required for the implementation of the tool in your organisation?

- Technical resources, IT: Did you experience any technical issues that required additional assistance?
- Upskilling: Going forward, will any training or upskilling be required?
- Legal support: Was any legal support required in filling out the tool?
- Other support required: Did implementation require significant involvement from any other departmental or even external support?

5. Barriers and facilitators [15 mins]

a. What were the main challenges or obstacles you faced during the pilot?

- [Participants in phase one] Did you notice improvement from round 1 to round 2?
- Did you identify any bugs? Were the existing bugs fixed?
- Tool functionality and automation?
- Was the time efficiency of the tool an issue for you?
- Anything else that could emerge as a barrier in your judgement?
- What advice would you give to others planning to use this tool?
- What helped you or could use them in performing the task?

6. Transferability and sustainability + DQ enhancements [15 mins]

a. Article 78 of the European Health Data Space Regulation (the EHDS Regulation)

mandates labelling health datasets within the EU to show their quality and usefulness, therefore applying this label will become required for all electronic health datasets collected and processed with the support of EU or national public funding from 2029. In your opinion, what must be in place before scaling the tool to other datasets and areas?

- Do you think this tool would work for other datasets in your organisation?
- How well does the tool integrate with your existing systems?
- What are your thoughts on the interoperability with this tool and your organisation's existing data management procedures and datasets?
- Are there foreseeable challenges to rolling it out more broadly, applying it to many datasets instead of 1 or 2?
- What changes (if any) would be required in order to do this? What additional support will be required to implement this tool on an ongoing basis?
- Who will be responsible for coordinating completion each year?
- Any additional changes required in the institutional governance? Has this tool changed or will it change how you or your team approach data quality?
- How will you / your organisation use it to improve some aspects, or what would you recommend to others in this regard?
- Data management in general - data quality management - data quality itself
- Processes - content (information on data quality) - technically

7. Other questions [10 mins]

- Have you used any other data quality tools before? If so, how does this one compare – if time?
- Do you have any recommendations for the improvement of the tool?
- Is there anything else that we've not covered today that you'd like to highlight or discuss?

Close

- Next steps: This is phase 2 of the pilot phase of the QUANTUM tool. The next step is to report the findings from this pilot to the EU in the form of a written report to recommend how to further develop it and what to consider for implementation. This covers the content and technical level.
- Another outcome this will contribute to are policy recommendations dealing with the governance and 'systemic' aspects to inform the pending Implementing Act and Delegated Act.
- Thanks for taking part.
- If you have any further queries, you can contact us by emailing [insert mail address].

Annex III - Feedback survey

Once finished each of the mid-scale pilot rounds, an online survey was sent out to all the participants to get some structured feedback, without preventing those who wished from also sending a more extensive report in a separate document.

Below is the list of questions included in the survey

- Which tool have you used?
- If you have used the docker version, have you faced any issues within the installation (docker)?
- Which assessment did you complete? Only quality and utility, or also maturity label?

(For those carrying out the pilot in both rounds, after the second round)

- Have you perceived an improvement in the usability or explainability of the current version of the tool?
- Have you improved the quality score in this round compared to the previous one?

(For all the participants)

- Did you find the tool intuitive, for example, was it easy to use and could you complete without the need of training or further information?
- Did you understand the dimensions clearly?
- Are the specifications of the data quality dimensions clear?
- Were the questions clear?
- Were the answers to the questions clear?
- Did you struggle with the maturity assessment? If so, please provide further information.
- Do you have any other suggestions for improvement of the tool or the Data Quality and Utility label?
- Do you have any other comments on your experience with piloting the tool?